

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part XI: Hepatitis E infection

Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez
CIMO Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza,
Portugal

On request from the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES) in coordination with Pauline Kooh and Moez Sanaa

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 78 primary studies investigating risk factors for sporadic infection with hepatitis E, which were conducted between 1986 and 2016. From these, only one study investigated exposures in children, six in immunocompromised individuals, five in pregnant women and seventy in the mixed population. These primary studies provided 599 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 60% of the meta-analytical data produced by observational studies from France (80 ORs), China (70 ORs), Mexico (44 ORs), Germany (35 ORs), USA (30 ORs), Nigeria (25 ORs), Tunisia (25 ORs), Italy (23 ORs) and UK (22 ORs). Seventy-three studies (~93.5%) employed an unmatched experimental design and produced a total of 513 ORs. From these, 348 reported or computed ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (i.e., crude ORs), while the other 165 ORs were adjusted by using unconditional logistic regressions. On the other hand, only five studies (~6.5%) employed a matched experimental design, providing for meta-analysis a total of 86 ORs. Most of them were estimated by Mantel-Haenzel method (49) and conditional logistic regression (25). After methodological quality assessment, two primary studies were marked as being possibly affected by selection, which yielded a total of 10 potentially-biased ORs. Within the pathways of transmission, the lowest share (~8%) of data came from person-to-person contagion, whereas data related with environmental routes (145 ORs), animal contact (139 ORs) and consumption of food (150 ORs) were similarly distributed.

Among the global risk categories in the mixed population, the group of environmental pathways was the most important risk factor for hepatitis E infection (overall OR=2.10; 95% 1.67 – 2.65); unlike the immunocompromised individuals (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.94 – 1.60) who were more exposed to hepatitis E infection by host-specific factors (overall OR=2.50; 95% CI: 1.70 – 3.69). In the mixed population, the global routes of meat consumption (overall OR=1.90; 95% CI: 1.53 – 2.37), contact with animals (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.51 – 2.06) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI:

1.34 – 2.26) came out as more relevant sources of hepatitis E than the host-specific factors (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.04). In the mixed population, travel (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 1.05 – 1.85) and consumption of seafood (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.11 – 1.54), although still significant, bore the lowest association with hepatitis E. Nonetheless, seafood emerged as an important vehicle for transmission of disease in the immunocompromised population (overall OR=2.12; 95% CI: 1.31 – 3.44), followed by meat (overall OR=1.60; 95% CI: 1.11 – 2.31). In pregnant females, the animal-related routes turned out to bear higher association with hepatitis E virus (overall OR=2.32; 95% CI: 1.93 – 2.79) than consumption of foods (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.91 – 2.52) and the environmental pathways as a whole (overall OR=1.20; 95% CI: 1.02 – 1.41).

Comparing among the disaggregated pathways of exposure to hepatitis E, the most important risk factors for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed population were contact with waste, sewage or lack of sanitation (overall OR=2.55; 95% CI: 1.76 – 3.68), suffering from a chronic illness (overall OR=2.51; 95% CI: 1.74 – 3.62), and consumption of processed meats of pork origin (overall OR=2.29; 95% CI: 1.89 – 2.78) and pork meat itself (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.83 – 2.83). Living on a farm (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.68 – 2.92) and consumption of meat-based RTE foods (overall OR=2.17; 95% CI: 1.23 – 3.82) could be at least as important sources of hepatitis E as the best-known risk factors of occupational contact with live/dead animals (overall OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.79 – 2.39) and drinking untreated/non-boiled water (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 1.64 – 2.58). Following processed meat, pork meat and RTE meats, food vehicles such as raw milk (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.28 – 2.92) and offal/live/pigeon meat/non-specific meats (other meats; overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.36 – 2.01) bore a comparable level of risk to person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.34 – 2.26) and suffering from an immunological disorder (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.29). The animal-related routes of contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.58; 95% CI: 1.25 – 2.01), wild animals (hunting and contact with rodents; overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 0.78 – 3.03) and contact with pets (overall OR=1.49; 95% CI: 1.21 – 1.83) bore stronger association with hepatitis E infection in the mixed population than the consumption of fish (overall OR=1.44; 95% CI: 1.05 – 1.98), red meats other than beef (overall OR=1.41; 95% CI: 1.16 – 1.72), molluscs (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 1.26 – 1.56) and fresh vegetables (overall OR=1.12; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.19).

In HIV and solid-organ transplant patients, the host-specific factors of suffering from a chronic condition (overall OR=7.81; 95% CI: 2.96 – 20.6), other medical conditions (overall OR=4.84; 95% CI: 1.53 – 15.33) and blood transfusion history/therapy with antiretrovirals (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.01 – 3.22) were more important risk factors for acquiring hepatitis E infection than the environmental routes of gardening/camping (overall OR=1.34; 95% CI: 0.89 – 2.01), drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.21; 95% CI: 0.67 – 2.18) and living on a farm (overall OR=1.13; 95% CI: 0.67 – 1.91). Pregnant women in occupational contact with animals were the most exposed to hepatitis E virus (overall OR=3.18; 95% CI: 2.20 – 4.59), followed by those in contact with other animals, namely, farm animals (overall OR=2.12; 95% CI: 1.52 – 2.97) and pets (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 1.56 – 2.72). The consumption of untreated water by pregnant females could also represent an important determinant of disease (overall OR=1.30; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.74),

Minor (or not statistically proven) factors for acquiring the disease were: consumption of beef (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.75), contact with garden, soil or forest (overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 1.11 – 1.48), suffering from other medical conditions (overall OR=1.28; 95% CI:

0.94 – 1.73) and international travel (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.57) in the mixed population; and the consumption of rabbit/venison/snake meat (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.82 – 2.79) and vegetables (overall OR=1.32; 95% CI: 0.89 – 1.97), and living on a farm (overall OR=0.91; 95% CI: 0.71 – 1.16) in the pregnant population.

On meta-analysis, people who ate beef/pork/other red meats/non-specific meats and became ill with hepatitis E infection were 1.456 times (95% CI: 0.957 – 2.217) more likely to have consumed it raw or undercooked than those who consumed the same type of meat but did not acquire the disease. By contrast, in the case of fresh vegetables, the fact of consuming them in raw state did not increase the overall risk of acquiring the disease, although consuming them unwashed increased the odds of acquiring hepatitis E virus by 1.384 times (95% CI: 0.936 – 2.05). Therefore, the practices of “consuming raw/undercooked red meats” (p=0.079) and “consuming unwashed vegetables” (p=0.100) represent on their own significant risk factors for acquiring hepatitis E virus.

3. Results

3.11 *Hepatitis E*

3.11.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors for human infection with Hepatitis E, a total of 614 clean bibliographic sources were identified using appropriate keywords in five bibliographic search engines, from which 93 case-control and cohort studies passed the full assessment for eligibility (Figure 1). From these, fifteen fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. Meta-analysis was undertaken on data either extracted or calculated from 78 primary studies – cohort and case-control studies – focusing on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted in years spanning from 1986 and 2016. Table 1 compiles a list of the primary studies along with their main features. The eligible studies jointly provided 599 odds-ratios categorised for meta-analysis. A total of 65 ORs were retrieved from 13 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 534 ORs were excerpted from 65 case-control studies performed after 2000. Meta-analytical data were obtained from primary studies conducted in 37 countries, although studies from only 9 countries generated ~60% of the ORs retrieved. These were: France (80 ORs), China (70 ORs), Mexico (44 ORs), Germany (35 ORs), USA (30 ORs), Nigeria (25 ORs), Tunisia (25 ORs), Italy (23 ORs) and UK (22 ORs) (Figure 2, top).

Primary studies investigated risk factors in different types of population, namely children (1 study), mixed population (70 studies), immunocompromised individuals (6 studies) and pregnant females (5 studies). Whenever the amount of data allowed, separate meta-analyses were adjusted on the mixed population (490 ORs plus 11 ORs from children), immunocompromised (54 ORs) and pregnant (44 ORs) population (Figure 2, bottom left). Only five case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 86 categorised ORs, which represented 14.3% of the data. Of these, only 10 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis whereas 76 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated by Mantel-Haenzel method (49) and conditional logistic regression (25) and a few estimated by chi-square (9) and unconditional logistic (3).

From the 73 studies that applied an unmatched design, a total of 513 ORs were extracted or calculated, which constituted 85.6% of the meta-analytical data. A total of 388 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 125 in multivariate analysis. Most of the ORs from unmatched designs were computed using chi-square (348) whilst 165 ORs were obtained from unconditional logistic regressions. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 434 ORs (72% of the data) were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 165 ORs (40%) were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control or cohort studies of hepatitis E infection

*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control and cohort studies of sporadic hepatitis E by country (top left), population type (bottom left) and pathway of exposure (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control and cohort studies of sporadic hepatitis E infection by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), study period with cut-off year 2000 (bottom left) and type of diagnosis test (bottom right). ELISA test can target IgG, IgM or both

Table 1. Characteristics of the 78 primary studies investigating risk factors for acquiring sporadic hepatitis E included in the meta-analysis

Study	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model	# ill/ non-ill	Quality #ORs/Removed*
Adjei et al. 2009	Ghana	Jan-May 2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	40 ill 65 non-ill	Good 7
Alavian et al. 2015	Iran	Jun 2012	Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	105 ill 445 non-ill 77 ill 192 non-ill	Good 9
Al-Naaimi et al. 2012	Iraq	Mar2010-2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	42 ill 2628 non-ill	Good 7
Alvarado et al. 2014a	Mexico	Aug2007-Feb 2008	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	25 ill 414 non-ill	Good 21/1
Alvarado et al. 2014b	Mexico	Dec2006-Aug 2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	100 ill 173 non-ill	Good 11
Alvarado et al. 2015	Mexico	2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	10 ill 136 non-ill	Good 10/4
Alvarez et al. 1999	Mexico	1987-1988	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	373 ill 3176 non-ill	Good 2
Ayoola et al. 2002	Saudi Arabia	2001	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	83 ill 400 non-ill	Good 1
Bawazir et al. 2010	Yemen	Apr-Jul 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	38 ill 318 non-ill	Good 8
Begum et al. 2009	India	Dec2006-Nov 2007	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	101 ill 199 non-ill	Good 3
Carpentier et al. 2012	France	2002-2003	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	159 ill 334 non-ill	Good 6
Caruso et al. 2016	Italy	2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	5 ill 37 non-ill	Good 7/1
Cevrioglu et al. 2004	Turkey	Jan 2000 - Jul2002	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	9 ill 67 non-ill	Good 1
Ceylan et al. 2003	Turkey	2003	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	18 ill 73 non-ill	Good 1
Chaussade et al. 2013	France	Oct 2011-Apr2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	302 ill 557 non-ill	Good 23/4
Cong et al. 2014	China	Jun 2011-Jul 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	208 ill 682 non-ill	Good 7
Cong et al. 2015	China	Jun 2011-Jul 2013	Susceptible Mixed	Unmatched Unmached	Uni-Chi Uni-Chi	160 ill 830 non-ill 244 ill 721 non-ill	Good 16
Cui et al. 2016	China	Dec2014-Apr 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	228 ill 799 non-ill	Good 7
Da Silva et al. 2012	Brazil	Jul 2009-Jan 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	26 ill 284 non-ill	Good 11
Delarocque et al. 2012	Egypt	2002-2007	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL	17 ill 68 hep A	Poor 7
Ditah et al. 2014	USA	2009-2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	490 ill 8324 non-ill	Good 6
Eldin et al. 2010	Egypt	Mar2007-Aug 2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	42 ill 133 non-ill	Good 4
Gad et al. 2011	Egypt	2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	68 ill 48 non-ill	Good 1
Galiana et al. 2008	Spain	Oct 2004-Jul 2007	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	23 ill 175 non-ill	Good 4
Galiana et al. 2010	Spain	2009	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	25 ill 187 non-ill	Good 4
Gomatos et al. 1996	Egypt	May1993-Jun1994	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	31 ill 17 non-ill	Good 4/1

Hannachi et al. 2011	Tunisia	Sep- Nov 2006	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	49 ill 355 non-ill	Good 11
Harrison et al. 2013	UK	2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL	154 ill 591 non-ill	Good 2
Hinjoy et al. 2013	Thailand	Nov2010- Apr 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	118 ill 395 non-ill	Good 6
Houcine et al. 2013	Tunisia	Set-Jun 2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	37 ill 650 non-ill	Good 14
Junaid et al. 2014	Nigeria	2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	200 ill 414 non-ill	Good 25
Kang et al. 2016	China	Jul 2013- May 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	330 ill 870 non-ill	Good 23
Kantala et al. 2016	Finland	2009	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	37 ill 348 non-ill	Good 1
Keane et al. 2012	UK	Jul 2009 - May 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-UL	102 ill 104 non-ill	Good 4
Kondili et al. 2006	Albania	1995	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	109 ill 236 non-ill	Good 15
			Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	40 ill 69 non-ill	
Kotwal et al. 2014	India	2010- 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	712 ill 3463 non-ill	Good 8
Krumbholz et al. 2012	Germany	Dec2007- Apr 2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	30 ill 132 non-ill	Good 4
Kuniholm et al. 2009	USA	1988- 1994	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL	4634 ill 1202non-ill	Good 16
Labrique et al. 2013	Bangladesh	2011	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	24 ill 68 non-ill	Good 16
Lagler et al. 2014	Austria	Apr-Set 2009	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	142 ill 855 non-ill	Good 16
Lanini et al. 2015	Italy	2002- 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	60 ill 1056 non-ill	Good 12
Legrand-Abrevanel et al. 2010	France	Jan 2004 - Jun 2009	Susceptible	Matched	Uni-MH Uni-Chi	38 ill 150 non-ill	Good 25
Liang et al. 2014	China	2011- 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	129 ill 178 non-ill	Good 1
Madden et al. 2016	South Africa	Fev 2014- Fev 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	320 ill 814 non-ill	Good 12
Mansuy et al. 2015	France	Oct 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	1311 ill 2042 non-ill	Good 26
Mast et al. 1997	USA	Nov1993- Mar 1994	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	70 ill 4937 non-ill	Good 4
Meader et al. 2010	UK	1991- 1995	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	10 ill 457 non-ill	Good 5/2
Mellgren et al. 2017	Sweden	Apr 2013- May 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	62 ill 142 non-ill	Poor 3
					Uni-Chi	146 ill 558 non-ill	Good 1
Meng et al. 2002	USA	1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	96 ill 544 non-ill	Good 3
Meng et al. 2015	China	May 2013 - Jul 2014	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	224 ill 1276 non-ill	Good 11/1
Nubling et al. 2002	Germany	2001	Adult	Unmatched	Multi-UL	20 ill 491 non-ill	Good 2
Olsen et al. 2006	Sweden	2005	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	25 ill 198 non-ill	Good 1
Pisano et al. 2016	Argentina	2016	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	16 ill 59 non-ill	Good
			Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	28 ill 514 non-ill	13/1
Psichogiou et al. 1995	Greece	Feb1986 - May 1990	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	22 ill 492 non-ill	Good 4

Rapicetta et al. 2013	Italy	2000-2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	113 ill 855 non-ill	Good 2
Rivero-Barciela et al. 2014	Spain	Jan 2011-May 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	87 ill 1286 non-ill	Good 7
Saffar et al. 2009	Iran	Jan- Dec 2003	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	25 ill 1055 non-ill	Good 1
Said et al. 2014	UK	Jun-Jul 2011	Mixed	Matched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	25 ill 75 non-ill	Good 11
Shimakawa et al. 2016	Gambia	Apr-Set 2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	28 ill 176 non-ill	Good 14
Scotto et al. 2015	Italy	Jan 2012 - Aug 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	26 ill 655 non-ill	Good 2
Taha et al. 2015	Malawi	1989-2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	132 ill 668 non-ill	Good 4
Tei et al. 2004	Japan	2003	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	9 ill 81 non-ill	Good 3
Teixeira et al. 2017	Portugal	Set-Nov 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	35 ill 79 non-ill	Good 4
Trautwein et al. 1995	Germany	Apr- Aug 1993	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	21 ill 1004 non-ill	Good 2
Tucker et al. 1996	South Africa	1996	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	82 ill 685 non-ill	Good 1
Unzueta et al. 2016	USA	Mar-Aug 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	32 ill 301 non-ill	Good 1
Vaidya et al. 2003	India	2002	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	95 ill 198 non-ill	Good 5
VanDerBerg et al. 2014	Netherlands	1994-2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	169 ill 391 non-ill	Good 4
Verhoef et al. 2012	Netherlands	2006-2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	134 ill 6938 non-ill	Good 10
Vilibic-Cavlek et al. 2016	Croatia	Jun 2014-Jul 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	12 ill 202 non-ill	Good 13/1
Villalba et al. 2013	Cuba	Feb-May 2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	38 ill 68 non-ill	Good 2
Villalba et al. 2010	Cuba	May-Aug 2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	47 ill 422 non-ill	Good 3
Vitral et al. 2014	Brazil	Mar-Apr 2004	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	50 ill 339 non-ill	Good 3
Wichmann et al. 2008	Germany	May2000-Aug 2007	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	45 ill 135 non-ill	Good 27
Wong et al. 2004	China	Mar- May 2001	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	176 ill 755 non-ill	Good 1
Wu et al. 1998	Taiwan	May1990-1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	18 ill 48 non-ill	Good 1
Yoon et al. 2014	Republic Korea	2007-2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	144 ill 2306 non-ill	Good 2
Zheng et al. 2006	China	2002-2004	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	1005 ill 715 non-ill	Good 4

(*) Number of ORs removed for having mean values below 0.5.

During methodological quality assessment, potential for selection bias was assigned to two case-control studies. While in Delarocque et al. (2012), the controls were hepatitis A positive, in Mellgreen et al. (2017), the associations between host-specific factors and hepatitis E were measured in patients with chronic hepatitis C. The ten ORs extracted from the studies above were marked as having potential for bias, and their influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused much more on the multiple pathways of transmission (471 ORs) than on host-specific factors (104 ORs) or travel (24 ORs). None of the primary studies investigated whether breastfeeding could exert any protective effect

against hepatitis E. Within the pathways of transmission, the data was equally distributed between animal (139 ORs), environmental (145 ORs) and food (150 ORs) sources (Figure 2, bottom right). Person-to-person contagion, however, presented the lowest share (7.8%) of data among the pathways of transmission. General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, study period and potential for bias status.

3.10.1 Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal-, food-related and person-to-person pathways of transmission

Study period was found to be influential only in the host-specific and environmental factors data partitions. In more recent years (after 2000), it appears that the host-specific factors, as a whole, became 4.3 times ($p=0.006$ in Table 3B) more associated with hepatitis E in immunocompromised individuals than in earlier years. Likewise, after the year 2000, the global environment pathways gained a greater importance as determinants of hepatitis E infection, increasing their pooled association with disease by 1.7 times ($p=0.095$ in Table 5B).

Table 2A. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring hepatitis E infection by geographical region for the mixed population (n=24 ORs)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.317	0.333	5	[0.662 – 1.971]	<.0001
South America	0.546	0.191	4	[0.172 – 0.920]	0.004
Europe(N,S,E,W)	0.041	0.015	15	[0.011 – 0.071]	0.008

Table 2B. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed population (n=24)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All Travel	0.333	0.145	24	[0.049 – 0.617]	0.022
(14 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad*	0.199 ^a	0.127	17	[-0.050 – 0.448]	0.117
	Any	0.537 ^{ab}	0.429	2	[-0.305 – 1.378]	0.211
	Inside**	0.953 ^b	0.333	5	[0.300 – 1.605]	0.004
	Before 2000					ND

Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2179	QE(df=21)	QM(df=3)
s^2 (residual)	0.6299	p=0.003	p=0.003
Publication bias	0.0001	0.0000	0.184
Points removed	0		

(*) Nationals of Mexico, Egypt and Bangladesh travelling inside

(**) Nationals of Mexico, Argentina, France, Spain, Italy, Austria, Germany, Netherlands, Taiwan and Japan travelling abroad

Figure 4. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of travel as a risk factor for hepatitis E infection in the mixed population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of host-specific factors for hepatitis E infection by region for the mixed (n=79) and the immunocompromised population (n=20)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed*					
Africa	0.311	0.145	13	[0.026 – 0.596]	0.032
Asia	0.633	0.147	11	[0.344 – 0.921]	<.0001
East Europe	1.081	0.189	11	[0.710 – 1.451]	<.0001
North America	0.071	0.132	9	[-0.188 – 0.329]	0.592
North Europe	0.694	0.182	6	[0.338 – 1.049]	<.0001
South America	0.222	0.136	10	[-0.045 – 0.489]	0.103
South Europe	1.108	0.224	7	[0.668 – 1.548]	<.0001
West Europe	0.580	0.147	12	[0.291 – 0.868]	<.0001
Immuno					
Asia	0.906	0.217	9	[0.481 – 1.331]	<.0001
Europe	0.473	0.183	11	[0.115 – 0.831]	0.010

(*) No breastfeeding data

Table 3B. Meta-analyses of host-specific factors for hepatitis E infection in the mixed (n=79) and the immunocompromised population (n=20)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (32 stud)	All host-specific	0.545	0.084	79	[0.379 – 0.711]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Chronic	0.920 ^c	0.187	13	[0.555 – 1.286]	<.0001
	Immuno	0.540 ^b	0.148	36	[0.251 – 0.829]	<.0001
	Other med	0.244 ^a	0.154	30	[-0.058 – 0.547]	0.114
	Before 2000					0.194
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1327	QE(df=76)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4641	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.040
Points removed	0					
Immuno (5 stud)	All host-specific	0.918	0.197	20	[0.532 – 1.305]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Chronic	2.056 ^c	0.495	9	[1.086 – 3.026]	<.0001
	Immuno	0.591 ^a	0.296	5	[0.011 – 1.170]	0.046
	Other med	1.577 ^b	0.588	6	[0.422 – 2.730]	0.007
	Before 2000	-1.465	0.539		[-2.521 - -0.409]	0.006
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0945	QE(df=16)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5731	p=0.085		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0036	0.0034			0.287
Points removed	0					

Figure 5. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for hepatitis E in the mixed (left) and the immunocompromised population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 3C. Meta-analysis on poor hygiene as risk factor for the transmission of hepatitis E in the mixed population – Africa (2 ORs)

Exposure	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
No handwashing after toilet (1 stud)	Fixed effects					
	All	0.388	0.302	2	[-0.203 – 0.980]	0.198
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=1)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.0387	p=0.745			

Figure 6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on no handwashing after going to toilet as a risk factor for hepatitis E infection in the mixed population

Table 4A. Meta-analysis of pathways related to animal contact for hepatitis E infection by region in the combined mixed (n=118) and immunocompromised (n=4) population and pregnant women (n=17)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed & Immuno					
Africa	1.085	0.165	19	[0.761 – 1.409]	<.0001
Asia	0.468	0.098	37	[0.276 – 0.660]	<.0001
North America	0.401	0.182	8	[0.043 – 0.758]	0.028
North Europe	0.541	0.209	10	[0.130 – 0.952]	0.010
South America	0.305	0.207	14	[-0.101 – 0.711]	0.142
South Europe	1.410	0.299	6	[0.824 – 1.997]	<.0001
West Europe	0.276	0.157	28	[-0.033 – 0.584]	0.080
Pregnant					
Africa	0.186	0.323	4	[-0.447 – 0.818]	0.565
Asia	0.828	0.123	3	[0.586 – 1.070]	<.0001
South America	1.034	0.164	10	[0.713 – 1.355]	<.0001

Table 4B. Meta-analysis of pathways related to animal contact for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed (n=118) and immunocompromised (n=4) population and pregnant women (n=17)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (39 stud)	All animal	0.568	0.079	122	[0.413 – 0.723]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Farm animals	0.463 ^a	0.121	26	[0.226 – 0.699]	<.0001
	Occupational	0.726 ^b	0.074	63	[0.581 – 0.871]	<.0001
	Pets	0.398 ^a	0.107	30	[0.188 – 0.608]	<.0001
	Wild	0.431 ^{ab}	0.345	3	[-0.245 – 1.108]	0.212
	Before 2000					0.256
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1007	QE(df=118)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3459	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0001		0.183	
	Points removed	0				
Pregnant (3 stud)	All animal	0.841	0.094	17	[0.656 – 1.026]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Farm animals	0.753	0.171	3	[0.417 – 1.088]	<.0001
	Occupational	1.156	0.188	8	[0.788 – 1.524]	<.0001
	Pets	0.723	0.141	6	[0.446 – 1.000]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=14)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1868	p=0.486		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0008	0.0005		0.102	
	Points removed	0				

ND: Not determined as all studies were conducted after the year 2000

Figure 7. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of animal contact as risk factor for hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed and immunocompromised population (left) and pregnant women (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection by region in the mixed (n=123), immunocompromised (n=12) and pregnant (n=10) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.923	0.210	39	[0.511 – 1.336]	<.0001
Asia	0.582	0.183	37	[0.224 – 0.940]	0.001
East Europe	1.042	0.366	8	[0.323 – 1.760]	0.005
North America	-0.263	0.549	2	[-1.338 – 0.813]	0.632
North Europe	0.215	0.545	6	[-0.854 – 1.283]	0.694
South America	0.510	0.315	11	[-0.107 – 1.128]	0.105
West Europe	0.519	0.220	20	[0.088 – 0.951]	0.018
Immuno					
N+S America	-0.138	0.322	2	[-0.770 – 0.493]	0.668
West Europe	0.276	0.150	10	[-0.018 – 0.570]	0.066
Pregnant					
Africa	-0.017	0.214	4	[-0.438 – 0.402]	0.935
Asia	0.217	0.088	6	[0.045 – 0.388]	0.013

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed (n=120), immunocompromised (n=12) and pregnant (n=10) population – North America removed from the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed (36 stud)	All environment	0.745	0.117	120	[0.515 – 0.975]	<.0001	
	Fixed effects						
	Drink water	0.721 ^b	0.116	50	[0.493 – 0.948]	<.0001	
	Farm	0.795 ^b	0.140	33	[0.521 – 1.070]	<.0001	
	Playground*	0.247 ^a	0.073	17	[0.104 – 0.390]	0.001	
	Waste**	0.935 ^c	0.188	20	[0.565 – 1.304]	<.0001	
	Before 2000	-0.548	0.328		[-1.191 – 0.094]	0.095	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3164	QE(df=115)		QM(df=4)		
	s^2 (residual)	0.4547	p<.0001		p<.0001		
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0001			0.006	
	Points removed	0					
	Immuno (3 stud)	All environment	0.202	0.136	12	[-0.065 – 0.469]	0.138
Fixed effects							
Drink water		0.189 ^a	0.300	3	[-0.400 – 0.779]	0.529	
Farm		0.122 ^a	0.267	4	[-0.401 – 0.645]	0.647	
Playground***		0.294 ^a	0.207	4	[-0.111 – 0.700]	0.155	
Before 2000						ND	
Random effects							
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.0000	QE(df=8)		QM(df=3)		
s^2 (residual)		0.2291	p=0.747		p=0.453		
Publication bias		-0.0057	0.0036			0.108	
Points removed	0						
Pregnant (4 stud)	All environment	0.184	0.081	10	[0.024 – 0.343]	0.023	
	Fixed effects						
	Drink water	0.261 ^b	0.148	4	[-0.029 – 0.552]	0.078	
	Farm	-0.097 ^a	0.124	4	[-0.340 – 0.145]	0.432	
	Waste*****	0.543 ^c	0.156	2	[0.237 – 0.848]	0.001	
	Before 2000					ND	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=7)		QM(df=3)		
	s^2 (residual)	0.0709	p=0.161		p=0.001		

Publication bias	0.0003	0.0003	0.304
Points removed	0		

- (*) Contact with garden, soil, forest and wood
- (**) Contact with human faeces or lack of sanitation facilities
- (***) Gardening, camping
- (****) Includes 1 OR from waste water and 1 OR from playground exposure

Figure 8. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for hepatitis E infection in the mixed (top left), immunocompromised (top right) and pregnant (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 6A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of hepatitis E by region in the combined mixed (n=36) and pregnant (n=1) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All					
Africa	0.371	0.220	5	[-0.060 – 0.802]	0.091
Asia	0.479	0.168	9	[0.150 – 0.808]	0.004
East Europe	0.522	0.092	21	[0.342 – 0.703]	<.0001
North America	-0.062	0.102	2	[-0.262 – 0.138]	0.543

Table 6B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of hepatitis E in the combined mixed (n=34) and pregnant (n=1) population – North America removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All	Fixed effects					
(13 stud)	All	0.552	0.134	35	[0.289 – 0.815]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0878	QE(df=34)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.8854	p=0.115			
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0001			0.822
	Points removed	0				

Figure 9. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of hepatitis E in the mixed population

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection by geographical region in the mixed (n=110), immunocompromised (n=18) and pregnant (n=13) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.633	0.192	14	[0.256 – 1.009]	0.001
Asia	0.400	0.138	14	[0.129 – 0.669]	0.004
North America	0.163	0.196	8	[-0.221 – 0.574]	0.406
North Europe	0.756	0.209	24	[0.346 – 1.166]	0.001
South America	0.237	0.258	8	[-0.269 – 0.744]	0.358
West Europe	0.492	0.164	42	[0.171 – 0.813]	0.003
Immuno					
South America	0.424	0.250	6	[-0.065 – 0.914]	0.089
West Europe	0.608	0.163	12	[0.289 – 0.927]	<.0001
Pregnant					
Asia	0.010	0.119	3	[-0.222 – 0.242]	0.933
South America	0.954	0.193	10	[0.576 – 1.333]	<.0001

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed (n=92), immunocompromised (n=18) and pregnant (n=13) population – North and South America regions removed the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All foods	0.551	0.099	92	[0.357 – 0.744]	<.0001
(21 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Composite*	0.816 ^c	0.349	3	[0.132 – 1.500]	0.019
	Meat	0.643 ^c	0.112	67	[0.424 – 0.862]	<.0001
	Produce**	0.109 ^a	0.027	12	[0.056 – 0.162]	<.0001
	Seafood	0.267 ^b	0.083	10	[0.104 – 0.430]	0.001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1069	QE(df=88)		QM(df=4)	
	s ² (residual)	0.3742	p<.0001		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.606
	Points removed	0				

Immuno	All foods	0.553	0.136	18	[0.286 – 0.820]	<.0001
(3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beverages***	0.386 ^{ab}	0.385	3	[-0.368 – 1.139]	0.316
	Meat	0.473 ^a	0.186	9	[0.108 – 0.838]	0.011
	Seafood	0.752 ^b	0.247	5	[0.268 – 1.235]	0.002
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=14)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.6402	p=0.179		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0067	0.0168			0.688
	Points removed	0				
Pregnant	All foods	0.412	0.261	13	[-0.099 – 0.924]	0.114
(3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dairy	1.407 ^b	0.452	2	[0.522 – 2.293]	0.002
	Meat****	0.413 ^a	0.313	7	[-0.200 – 1.027]	0.187
	Produce**	0.279 ^a	0.204	4	[-0.119 – 0.679]	0.170
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1744	QE(df=10)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1666	p=0.128		p=0.008	
	Publication bias	-0.0013	0.0004			0.001
	Points removed	0				

(*) Non-specific food eaten out

(**) Only vegetables

(***) Only bottled water

(****) Rabbit, venison, snake and BBQ meat

Figure 10. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed (top left), immunocompromised (top right) and pregnant (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 8A. Meta-analysis of meat consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=79), immunocompromised (n=9) and pregnant (n=7) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.855	0.218	7	[0.428 – 1.281]	<.0001
Asia	0.325	0.173	7	[-0.014 – 0.665]	0.060
North America	0.162	0.181	8	[-0.193 – 0.516]	0.371
North Europe	0.794	0.189	25	[0.424 – 1.164]	<.0001
South America	0.600	0.234	12	[0.141 – 1.060]	0.010
West Europe	0.588	0.144	36	[0.306 – 0.870]	<.0001

Table 8B. Meta-analysis of meat consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed (n=69), immunocompromised (n=9) and pregnant (n=7) population. North American region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed						
(18 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beef	0.312 ^a	0.356	3	[-0.386 – 1.011]	0.381
	Other red meat	0.346	0.100	21	[0.149 – 0.543]	0.001
	Other meats	0.503	0.099	18	[0.308 – 0.698]	<.0001
	Pork	0.821	0.111	19	[0.603 – 1.039]	<.0001
	Proc meat	0.829 ^a	0.099	24	[0.634 – 1.023]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
Random effects						
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0730	QE(df=80)		QM(df=5)	
	s ² (residual)	0.3675	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.129
	Points removed	0				

Figure 11. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of meat consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed, immunocompromised and pregnant population

Table 9A. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=10) and immunocompromised (n=5) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa+Asia+S.A*	0.241	0.102	5	[0.041 – 0.442]	0.018
West Europe	0.373	0.057	10	[0.260 – 0.485]	<.0001

(*) Data from Africa (2 ORs), South America (2 ORs) and Asia (1 OR) were merged.

Table 9B. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed (n=10) and immunocompromised (n=5) population. No geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed						
(6 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Fish*	0.368 ^a	0.161	4	[0.052 – 0.684]	0.023
	Molluscs**	0.339 ^a	0.053	11	[0.235 – 0.442]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=13)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5346	p=0.016		p=0.862	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.435
	Points removed	0				

(*) Fish and 1 OR from UndefinedS

(**) Shellfish

Figure 12. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed and immunocompromised population

Table 10. Meta-analysis of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed (n=3) and pregnant (n=2) population (4 ORs from South America and 1 OR from Asia)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (4 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Raw milk	0.659 ^a	0.210	5	[0.246 – 1.071]	0.002
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0567	QE(df=4)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.3582	p=0.182			
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0001		0.370	
Points removed	0					

Figure 13. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed and pregnant population

Table 11A. Meta-analysis of vegetables consumption as a pathway for acquiring hepatitis E infection by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=12), immunocompromised (n=1) and pregnant (n=4) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa/S.Am*	0.414	0.196	8	[0.030 – 0.800]	0.035
Asia	0.031	0.102	3	[-0.169 – 0.230]	0.764
West Europe	0.090	0.024	6	[0.043 – 0.136]	<.0001

(*) Merged data from Africa (6 ORs) and South America (2 ORs)

Table 11B. Meta-analysis of vegetables consumption as a pathway for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed (n=12) and pregnant (n=4) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Mixed	0.089	0.023	12	[0.044 – 0.135]	<.0001
Pregnant	0.135	0.145	4	[-0.151 – 0.420]	0.355
Before 2000					ND
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=14)		QE(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.2397	p=0.854		p=0.001	
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.605
Points removed	0				

Figure 14. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of vegetables consumption as a pathway for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the combined mixed and pregnant population

3.11.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of hepatitis E infection by the consumption of meat-based ready-to-eat foods

As a whole, RTE foods of meat origin can be regarded as a potential vehicle for transmission of hepatitis E infection, as deduced from the integration of the outcomes from case-control studies undertaken in Northern Europe, Africa and South America (Table 12A). On meta-analysis, people who became infected with hepatitis E were 2.171 times (95% CI: 1.233 – 3.819) more likely to have consumed meat-based RTE food than those who did not get ill (Table 12B). The meat-based RTE foods comprised pork products such as salami, bacon, ham, pork pate and pork pie.

Table 12A. Meta-analysis of the consumption of RTE foods as a pathway for acquiring hepatitis E infection by geographical region in the mixed population (n=8)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	1.353	0.238	6	[0.886 – 1.820]	<.0001
Africa/S.Am*	0.407	0.138	2	[0.137 – 0.677]	0.003

(*) Merged data from Africa (1 OR) and South America (1 ORs)

Table 12B. Meta-analysis of the consumption of meat-based RTE foods as a pathway for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed population (n=8)

Population	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Meat RTE* Before 2000	0.775	0.288	8	[0.210 – 1.340]	0.007 ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1570	QE(df=7)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.4060	p=0.041			
	Publication bias	-0.0008	0.0003			0.001
	Points removed	0				

(*) Salami, bacon, ham, pork pate and pork pie

Figure 15. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the consumption of meat-based RTE foods as a pathway for acquiring hepatitis E infection in the mixed population

Figure 16. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on occupational exposure pathways of transmission of hepatitis E in the mixed (n=63) and pregnant population (n=8)

Figure 17. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on consumption of processed meats as a vehicle for transmission of hepatitis E in the mixed (n=24) and the immunocompromised population (n=2) ordered by country

Figure 18. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on consumption of pork meat as a vehicle for transmission of hepatitis E in the mixed (n=18) and the immunocompromised population (n=3) ordered by country

Figure 19. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on drinking water as a source of hepatitis E infection in the mixed (n=52), immunocompromised (n=3) and pregnant (n=4) population ordered by country

Figure 20. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on seafood as a source of hepatitis E infection in the mixed (n=10) and immunocompromised (n=5) population ordered by country

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled by means of two forest plots: the first forest plot (Figure 21) was designed for comparing among the *global* risk categories as potential determinants of hepatitis E infection in the mixed, immunocompromised and pregnant populations; and the other (Figure 22) for comparing among the *disaggregated* risk categories and specific pathways of exposure for the same populations. To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

In the mixed population (Figure 21), the group of environmental pathways was the most important risk factor for hepatitis E infection (overall OR=2.10; 95% 1.67 – 2.65). However, in the immunocompromised population, such pathways (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.94 – 1.60) bore the lowest association with hepatitis E infection, being the host-specific factors (overall OR=2.50; 95% CI: 1.70 – 3.69) the most important determinants of hepatitis E in HIV and solid-organ transplant patients. In the mixed population, the global routes of consumption of meat (overall OR=1.90; 95% CI: 1.53 – 2.37), contact with animals (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.51 – 2.06) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.34 – 2.26) came out as more relevant sources of hepatitis E than the host-specific factors (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.04). In the mixed population, travel (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 1.05 – 1.85) and consumption of seafood (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.11 – 1.54), although still significant, bore the lowest association with hepatitis E. Nonetheless, seafood emerged as an important source of disease in the immunocompromised population (overall

OR=2.12; 95% CI: 1.31 – 3.44), followed by foods (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.33 – 2.27), and, in particular, meat (overall OR=1.60; 95% CI: 1.11 – 2.31). In pregnant females, the animal-related pathways of transmission turned out to bear higher association with hepatitis E infection (overall OR=2.32; 95% CI: 1.93 – 2.79) than consumption of foods (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.91 – 2.52) and the global environmental pathways (overall OR=1.20; 95% CI: 1.02 – 1.41).

Comparing among the disaggregated pathways of exposure to hepatitis E (Figure 22), travel inside ranked first among the sources of hepatitis E infection. Nonetheless, since this outcome originated from only five observations in only three countries – Mexico, Egypt and Bangladesh, it would be misleading to consider travelling inside as the most important source of hepatitis E infection. In the mixed population, the most important risk factors for acquiring hepatitis E infection were, therefore, contact with waste, sewage or lack of sanitation (overall OR=2.55; 95% CI: 1.76 – 3.68), suffering from a chronic illness (overall OR=2.51; 95% CI: 1.74 – 3.62) and consumption of processed meats, mainly of pork origin (overall OR=2.29; 95% CI: 1.89 – 2.78), and pork meat itself (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.83 – 2.83). Living on a farm (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.68 – 2.92) and consumption of meat-based RTE foods (overall OR=2.17; 95% CI: 1.23 – 3.82) could be at least as important sources of hepatitis E as the well-known risk factors of occupational contact with live/dead animals (overall OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.79 – 2.39) and drinking untreated/non-boiled water (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 1.64 – 2.58).

Following processed meat, pork meat and RTE meats, food vehicles such as raw milk (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.28 – 2.92) and other meats including offal, liver, pigeon meat and non-specific meats (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.36 – 2.01) bore a comparable level of risk to person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.34 – 2.26) and suffering from an immunological disorder (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.29). The animal-related pathways of contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.58; 95% CI: 1.25 – 2.01), wild animals (hunting and contact with rodents; overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 0.78 – 3.03) and pets (overall OR=1.49; 95% CI: 1.21 – 1.83) bore stronger association with hepatitis E infection in the mixed population than the consumption of fish (overall OR=1.44; 95% CI: 1.05 – 1.98), red meats other than beef (overall OR=1.41; 95% CI: 1.16 – 1.72), molluscs (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 1.26 – 1.56), beef (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.75) and fresh vegetables (overall OR=1.12; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.19). Minor routes of transmission of hepatitis E in the mixed population were contact with garden, soil and forest (overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 1.11 – 1.48), suffering from other medical conditions (overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 0.94 – 1.73) and international travel (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.57).

In HIV and solid-organ transplant patients (viz. immunocompromised individuals), the host-specific factors of suffering from a chronic condition (overall OR=7.81; 95% CI: 2.96 – 20.6), other medical conditions (overall OR=4.84; 95% CI: 1.53 – 15.33) and blood transfusion history/therapy with antiretrovirals (Immuno; overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.01 – 3.22) were more important risk factors for acquiring hepatitis E infection than the environmental routes of gardening/camping (overall OR=1.34; 95% CI: 0.89 – 2.01), drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.21; 95% CI: 0.67 – 2.18) and living on a farm (overall OR=1.13; 95% CI: 0.67 – 1.91).

Pregnant women in occupational contact with live/dead animals were the most exposed to hepatitis E virus (overall OR=3.18; 95% CI: 2.20 – 4.59), followed by those in contact with

other animals, namely, farm animals (overall OR=2.12; 95% CI: 1.52 – 2.97) and pets (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 1.56 – 2.72). While, on meta-analysis, the consumption of untreated water by pregnant females could represent an important determinant of disease (overall OR=1.30; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.74), the consumption of rabbit/venison/snake meat (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.82 – 2.79) and vegetables (overall OR=1.32; 95% CI: 0.89 – 1.97) appeared as minor sources of hepatitis E infection. Pregnant women ‘living on a farm’ could not be proven to be more exposed to hepatitis E virus than those ‘living in an urban environment’ (overall OR=0.91; 95% CI: 0.71 – 1.16).

Figure 21. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring hepatitis E infection for global risk categories in the mixed, pregnant and immunocompromised population. The global risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

Figure 22. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring hepatitis E infection for disaggregated risk categories in the mixed, pregnant and immunocompromised population, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

3.11.4 Meta-analysis on the effect of handling food on the risk of transmission of hepatitis E

The only food data partitions comprising sufficient data that could support the assessment of the effect of handling were the red meats/other meats and the fresh vegetables disaggregated partitions. Full estimates and funnel plots of the meta-analyses on the effect of consuming raw meats and raw/unwashed vegetables are shown in the supplementary Tables S1 and S2, and Figures S1 and S2, respectively. For the hepatitis E infection meta-analysis, no data partition had sufficient information on setting; thus, the relative effect of eating food prepared outside the home on the overall association with disease could not be calculated.

Table 13. Meta-analysed effect of handling on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Red meats & other meats*	OR(Base)	1.590	1.289	1.960
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.456	0.957	2.217
Fresh vegetables	OR(Base)	1.092	1.043	1.144
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	0.972	0.796	1.186
	OR(Unwashed)/OR(Base)	1.384	0.936	2.050

*Beef (3 ORs), pork (21 ORs), other red meats (21 ORs) and non-specific meats (22 ORs)

On meta-analysis, people who ate beef/pork/other red meats/non-specific meats and became ill with hepatitis E infection were 1.456 times (95% CI: 0.957 – 2.217) more likely to have consumed it raw or undercooked than those who consumed the same type of meat but did not acquire the disease (Table 13). Hence, the practice of “consuming raw or undercooked red meats” represents on its own a significant risk factor for hepatitis E infection (p=0.079; Table S1). By contrast, in the case of fresh vegetables, the fact of consuming them in raw state did not increase the overall risk of acquiring the disease. However, the same cannot be said for the practice of not washing them, since this meta-analysis estimated that consuming unwashed vegetables increased the odds of acquiring hepatitis E virus by 1.384 times (95% CI: 0.936 – 2.05) that of the base scenario (Table 3). Therefore, the practice of “consuming unwashed vegetables” can be regarded as a risk factor for hepatitis E infection (p=0.10; Table S2).

3.11.5 Synthesis of the risks associated to poor handling of foods

All of the poor food handling habits explored in the primary studies related to lack of hand hygiene before eating (Figure 23). Infrequent, poor or no handwashing before having meals was proven to be associated with hepatitis E infection in some case-control studies, with mean ORs ranging from 1.04 to 2.09. When meta-analysed, no handwashing turned out to be a risky practice for disease transmission increasing the overall odds of acquiring hepatitis E infection by 1.420 times (95% CI: 1.190 – 1.680; Figure 23).

Figure 23. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring hepatitis E infection associated to poor handwashing before meals in the mixed population

4 Conclusions

4.11 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic hepatitis E infection

- ❖ The outcomes from 78 case-control and cohort studies investigating host-specific factors, travel and pathways of transmission for sporadic hepatitis E infection were meta-analysed within appropriate data partitions, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ In the mixed population, the most important *global* risk factors for hepatitis E infection are the environmental pathways (OR=2.10), consumption of meat (OR=1.90) and animal contact pathways (OR=1.76).
- ❖ In pregnant females, the most important *global* risk factor is the animal contact pathways (OR=2.32).
- ❖ In immunocompromised individuals, the most important *global* risk factors for hepatitis E infection are host-specific factors (OR=2.50), and consumption of seafood (OR=2.12) and meat (OR=1.60)
- ❖ Among the *disaggregated* pathways of exposure to hepatitis E, the most important risk factors in the mixed population are contact with waste (OR=2.55), suffering from a chronic illness (OR=2.51), and consumption of processed meats of pork origin (OR=2.29) and pork meat itself (OR=2.27).
- ❖ Living on a farm (OR=2.21) and consumption of meat-based RTE foods (OR=2.17) could be at least as important sources of hepatitis E as the best-known risk factors of occupational contact with live/dead animals (OR=2.07) and drinking untreated water (OR=2.06).
- ❖ Raw milk (OR=1.93) and offal/live/pigeon meat/non-specific meats (OR=1.65) bear a comparable level of risk to person-to-person contagion (OR=1.74) and suffering from an immunological disorder (OR=1.72).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the animal-related pathways of contact with farm animals (OR=1.58), wild animals (OR=1.54) and contact with pets (OR=1.49) bear stronger association with hepatitis E infection than the consumption of fish (OR=1.44), red meats other than beef (OR=1.41), molluscs (OR=1.40) and fresh vegetables (OR=1.12).
- ❖ In HIV and solid-organ transplant patients, the host-specific factors of suffering from a chronic condition (OR=7.81), other medical conditions (OR=4.84) and blood transfusion history/therapy with antiretrovirals (OR=1.81) are more important determinants of hepatitis E infection than the environmental routes of

gardening/camping (OR=1.34), drinking untreated water (OR=1.21) and living on a farm (OR=1.13).

- ❖ Pregnant women in occupational contact with live/dead animals are the most exposed to hepatitis E virus (OR=3.18), followed by those in contact with other animals, namely, farm animals (OR=2.12) and pets (OR=2.06).
- ❖ In the mixed population, minor risk factors for acquiring the disease are: consumption of beef (OR=1.37), contact with garden, soil or forest (OR=1.28), suffering from other medical conditions (OR=1.28) and international travel (OR=1.22).
- ❖ In the pregnant population, consumption of rabbit/venison/snake meat (OR=1.51) and vegetables (OR=1.32), and living on a farm (OR=0.91) are minor risk factors for acquiring hepatitis E infection.
- ❖ People who ate beef/pork/other red meats/non-specific meats and became ill with hepatitis E infection were ~1.5 times more likely to have consumed it raw or undercooked than those who consumed the same type of meat but did not acquire the disease.
- ❖ Not washing vegetables is a risk factor on its own, as it increases the odds of becoming ill with hepatitis E infection by ~1.4 times that of simply consuming fresh vegetables.

5 References

5.11 Seventy-eight case-control and cohort primary studies assessing risk factors for hepatitis E infection

Adjei, A. A.; Aviyase, J. T.; Tettey, Y.; Adu-Gyamfi, C.; Mingle, J. A. A.; Ayeh-Kumi, P. F.; Adiku, T. K. & Gyasi, R. K. (2009), 'Hepatitis E virus infection among pig handlers in Accra, Ghana.', *East African Medical Journal* **86**(8), 359--363.

Alavian, S. M.; Ataei, B.; Ebrahimi, A.; Pirhaji, O.; Azad, R.; Olya, B. & Ataei, A. M. (2015), 'Anti-Hepatitis E Antibody in Hemodialysis Patients in Isfahan, Iran: Prevalence and Risk Factors.', *Hepatitis Monthly* **15**(9), e23633.

Al-Naaimi, A.; Turkey, A.; Khaleel, H.; Jalil, R.; Mekhleef, O.; Kareem, S.; Hasan, N. & Dhadain, A. (2012), 'Predicting acute viral hepatitis serum markers (A and E) in patients with suspected acute viral hepatitis attending primary health care centers in Baghdad: a one year cross-sectional study.', *Global Journal of Health Science* **4**(5), 172--183.

Alvarado-Esquivel, C.; Sanchez-Anguiano, L. & Hernandez-Tinoco, J. (2014), 'Seroepidemiology of hepatitis E virus infection in general population in rural Durango, Mexico', *Hepatitis Monthly* **14**(6).

Alvarado-Esquivel, C.; Sánchez-Anguiano, L. & Hernández-Tinoco, J. (2014), 'Hepatitis E virus exposure in pregnant women in rural Durango, Mexico', *Annals of Hepatology* **13**(5), 510--517.

Alvarado-Esquivel, C.; Sanchez-Anguiano, L. F. & Hernandez-Tinoco, J. (2015), 'Seroepidemiology of hepatitis e virus infection in mennonites in Mexico.', *Journal of Clinical Medicine Research* **7**(2), 103--108.

Alvarez-Muñoz, M.; Torres, J.; Damasio, L.; Gómez, A.; Tapia-Conyer, R. & Muñoz, O. (1999), 'Seroepidemiology of hepatitis E virus infection in Mexican subjects 1 to 29 years of age', *Archives of Medical Research* **30**(3), 251--254.

Ayoola, E.; Want, M.; Gadour, M.; Al-Hazmi, M. & Hamza, M. (2002), 'Hepatitis E virus infection in haemodialysis patients: A case-control study in Saudi Arabia', *Journal of Medical Virology* **66**(3), 329--334.

Bawazir, A. b.; Hart, C.; Sallam, T.; Parry, C.; Beeching, N. & Cuevas, L. (2010), 'Seroepidemiology of hepatitis A and hepatitis E viruses in Aden, Yemen', *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* **104**(12), 801--805.

Begum, N.; Devi, S. G.; Husain, S. A. & Kar, P. (2009), 'Seroprevalence of subclinical HEV infection in pregnant women from north India: a hospital based study.', *The Indian Journal of Medical Research* **130**(6), 709--713.

Carpentier, A.; Chaussade, H.; Rigaud, E.; Rodriguez, J. d.; Berthault, C.; Boué, F.; Tognon, M.; Touzé, A.; Garcia-Bonnet, N.; Choutet, P. c. & Coursaget, P. (2012), 'High hepatitis E virus seroprevalence in forestry workers and in wild boars in France', *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* **50**(9), 2888--2893.

Caruso, C.; Peletto, S.; Rosamilia, A.; Modesto, P.; Chiavacci, L.; Sona, B.; Balsamelli, F.; Ghisetti, V.; Acutis, P. L.; Pezzoni, G.; Brocchi, E.; Vitale, N. & Masoero, L. (2016), 'Hepatitis E Virus: A Cross-Sectional Serological and Virological Study in Pigs and Humans at Zoonotic Risk within a High-Density Pig Farming Area.', *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*.

Cevrioglu, A. e.; Altindis, M.; Tanir, H. & Aksoy, F. (2004), 'Investigation of the incidence of hepatitis E virus among pregnant women in Turkey', *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Research* **30**(1), 48--52.

Ceylan, A.; Ertem, M.; Ilcin, E. & Ozekinci, T. (2003), 'A special risk group for hepatitis E infection: Turkish agricultural workers who use untreated waste water for irrigation', *Epidemiology and Infection* **131**(1), 753--756.

Chaussade, H.; Rigaud, E.; Allix, A.; Carpentier, A.; Touzé, A.; Delzescaux, D.; Choutet, P.; Garcia-Bonnet, N. & Coursaget, P. (2013), 'Hepatitis E virus seroprevalence and risk factors for individuals in working contact with animals', *Journal of Clinical Virology* **58**(3), 504 -- 508.

Cong, W.; Sui, J.-C.; Zhang, X.-Y.; Qian, A.-D.; Chen, J. & Zhu, X.-Q. (2015), 'Seroprevalence of Hepatitis E Virus Among Pregnant Women and Control Subjects in China', *Journal of Medical Virology* **87**(3), 446--450.

Cong, W. b.; Meng, Q.-F.; Li, B.; Ma, F.-L.; Qian, A.-D.; Wang, X.-Y.; Yu, C.-Z. & Zhu, X.-Q. b. (2014), 'Seroprevalence of hepatitis E virus infection in psychiatric patients and control subjects in Shandong Province, eastern China', *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* **28**, e70--e73.

Cui, W.; Sun, Y.; Xu, A.; Gao, R.; Gong, L.; Zhang, L. & Jiang, M. (2016), 'Hepatitis E seroprevalence and related risk factors among seafood processing workers: a cross-sectional survey in Shandong Province, China', *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* **49**, 62 -- 66.

Da Silva, S.; de Oliveira, J.; Vitral, C. c.; de Almeida Vieira, K.; Pinto, M. & Dutra Souto, F. (2012), 'Prevalence of hepatitis E virus antibodies in individuals exposed to swine in Mato Grosso, Brazil', *Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz* **107**(3), 338--341.

Delarocque-Astagneau, E.; Abravanel, F.; Moshen, A.; Le Foulher, L.; Gad, R. R.; El-Daly, M.; Ibrahim, E. M.; El-Aidy, S.; Lashin, T.; El-Hoseiny, M.; Izopet, J.; Mohamed, M. K.; Fontanet, A. & Hamid, M. A. (2012), 'Epidemiological and virological characteristics of symptomatic acute hepatitis E in Greater Cairo, Egypt', *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* **18**(10), 982--988.

Ditah, I.; Ditah, F.; Devaki, P.; Ditah, C.; Kamath, P. & Charlton, M. (2014), 'Current

epidemiology of hepatitis E virus infection in the United States: Low seroprevalence in the National Health and Nutrition Evaluation Survey', *Hepatology* **60**(3), 815--822.

Eldin, S.; Seddik, I.; Daef, E.; Shata, M.; Raafat, M.; Abdel Baky, L. & Nafeh, M. (2010), 'Risk factors and immune response to hepatitis E viral infection among acute hepatitis patients in Assiut, Egypt.', *The Egyptian journal of immunology / Egyptian Association of Immunologists* **17**(1), 73--86.

Gad, Y.; Mousa, N.; Shams, M.; Elewa, A.; Al-Adrosy, H.; El-Desoky, A.-E. & Ahmad, N. (2011), 'Seroprevalence of subclinical HEV infection in asymptomatic, apparently healthy, pregnant women in Dakahlyia Governorate, Egypt', *Asian Journal of Transfusion Science* **5**(2), 136-139.

Galiana, C.; Fernández-Barredo, S.; García, A.; Gómez, M. & Pérez-Gracia, M. b. b. (2008), 'Short report: Occupational exposure to hepatitis e virus (HEV) in swine workers', *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* **78**(6), 1012--1015.

Galiana, C.; Fernndez-Barredo, S. & Prez-Gracia, M. (2010), 'Prevalence of hepatitis e virus (HEV) and risk factors in pig workers and blood donors [Prevalencia del virus de la hepatitis E (VHE) y factores de riesgo en trabajadores de explotaciones porcinas y donantes voluntarios]', *Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica* **28**(9), 602--607.

Gomatos, P.; Monier, M.; Arthur, R.; Rodier, G.; El-Zimaity, D.; Hassan, N.; Quinti, I.; El-Sahly, A.-D.; Sultan, Y. & Hyams, K. (1996), 'Sporadic acute hepatitis caused by hepatitis E virus in Egyptian adults', *Clinical Infectious Diseases* **23**(1), 195--196.

Hannachi, N.; Hidar, S.; Harrabi, I.; Mhalla, S.; Marzouk, M.; Ghzel, H.; Ghannem, H.; Khairi, H. & Boukadida, J. (2011), 'Seroprevalence and risk factors of hepatitis E among pregnant women in central Tunisia. [Séroprévalence et facteurs de risque de l'hépatite virale E chez la femme enceinte dans le centre tunisien]', *Pathologie Biologie* **59**(5), e115--e118.

Harrison, A.; Scobie, L.; Crossan, C.; Parry, R.; Johnston, P.; Stratton, J.; Dickinson, S.; Ellis, V.; Hunter, J.; Prescott, O.; Madden, R.; Lin, N.; Henley, W.; Bendall, R. f. & Dalton, H. f. (2013), 'Hepatitis E seroprevalence in recipients of renal transplants or haemodialysis in southwest England: A case-control study', *Journal of Medical Virology* **85**(2), 266--271.

Hinjoy, S. b.; Nelson, K.; Gibbons, R.; Jarman, R.; Mongkolsirichaikul, D.; Smithsuwan, P.; Fernandez, S.; Labrique, A. & Patchanee, P. (2013), 'A Cross-Sectional Study of Hepatitis E Virus Infection in Healthy People Directly Exposed and Unexposed to Pigs in a Rural Community in Northern Thailand', *Zoonoses and Public Health* **60**(8), 555--562.

Houcine, N.; Jacques, R.; Salma, F.; Anne-Gaëlle, D.; Amin, S.; Mohsen, H.; Hamadi, B.; Christophe, R.; Patrice, A.; Mahjoub, A. & Caroline, S. (2012), 'Seroprevalence of hepatitis E virus infection in rural and urban populations, Tunisia', *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* **18**(5), E119 -- E121.

Junaid, S. b.; Agina, S. & Abubakar, K. (2014), 'Epidemiology and associated risk factors of hepatitis E virus infection in Plateau State, Nigeria', *Virology: Research and Treatment* **5**, 15--26.

Kang, Y.-H.; Cong, W.; Zhang, X.-Y.; Wang, C.-F.; Shan, X.-F. & Qian, A.-D. (2016), 'Hepatitis E virus seroprevalence among farmers, veterinarians and control subjects in Jilin province, Shandong province and Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, China.', *Journal of medical virology*.

Kantala, T.; Kinnunen, P. c. f.; Oristo, S.; Jokelainen, P. b. d.; Vapalahti, O. c. e. & Maunula, L. (2016), 'Hepatitis E Virus Antibodies in Finnish Veterinarians', *Zoonoses and Public Health*.

Keane, F. E.; Gompels, M.; Bendall, R. P.; Drayton, R.; Jennings, L.; Black, J.; Baragwanath, G.; Lin, N. X.; Henley, W. E.; Ngui, S.-L.; Ijaz, S. & Dalton, H. R. (2012), 'Hepatitis E virus coinfection in patients with HIV infection', *HIV Medicine* **13**(1), 83--88.

Kondili, L.; Chionne, P.; Porcaro, A.; Madonna, E.; Taffon, S.; Resuli, B.; Taliani, G. & Rapicetta, M. (2006), 'Seroprevalence of hepatitis E virus (HEV) antibody and the possible association with chronic liver disease: a case-control study in Albania', *Epidemiology and Infection* **134**(1), 95--101.

Kotwal, A. b.; Singh, H.; Verma, A.; Gupta, R.; Jain, S.; Sinha, S.; Joshi, R.; Teli, P.; Khunga, V.; Bhatnagar, A. & Ranjan, R. (2014), 'A study of Hepatitis A and E virus seropositivity profile amongst young healthy adults in India', *Medical Journal Armed Forces India* **70**(3), 225--229.

Krumbholz, A.; Mohn, U.; Lange, J.; Motz, M.; Wenzel, J.; Jilg, W.; Walther, M.; Straube, E.; Wutzler, P. & Zell, R. (2012), 'Prevalence of hepatitis E virus-specific antibodies in humans with occupational exposure to pigs', *Medical Microbiology and Immunology* **201**(2), 239--244.

Kuniholm, M.; Purell, R.; McQuillan, G.; Engle, R.; Wasley, A. & Nelson, K. (2009), 'Epidemiology of hepatitis E virus in the United States: Results from the third national health and nutrition examination survey, 1988-1994', *Journal of Infectious Diseases* **200**(1), 48--56.

Labrique, A. B.; Zaman, K.; Hossain, Z.; Saha, P.; Yunus, M.; Hossain, A.; Ticehurst, J.; Kmush, B. & Nelson, K. E. (2013), 'An Exploratory Case Control Study of Risk Factors for Hepatitis E in Rural Bangladesh', *PLOS ONE* **8**(5).

Lagler, H.; Poepl, W.; Winkler, H.; Herkner, H.; Faas, A.; Mooseder, G. & Burgmann, H. (2014), 'Hepatitis E Virus Seroprevalence in Austrian Adults: A Nationwide Cross-Sectional Study among Civilians and Military Professionals', *PLOS ONE* **9**(2).

Lanini, S.; Garbuglia, A.; Lapa, D.; Puro, V.; Navarra, A.; Pergola, C.; Ippolito, G. & Capobianchi, M. (2015), 'Epidemiology of HEV in the mediterranean basin: 10-year prevalence in Italy', *BMJ Open* **5**(7).

Legrand-Abravanel, F.; Kamar, N.; Sandres-Saune, K.; Garrouste, C.; Dubois, M.; Mansuy, J.-M.; Muscari, F.; Sallusto, F.; Rostaing, L. & Izopet, J. (2010), 'Characteristics of autochthonous hepatitis E virus infection in solid-organ transplant recipients in France.', *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* **202**(6), 835--844.

Liang, H.; Su, S.; Deng, S.; Gu, H.; Ji, F.; Wang, L.; Liang, C.; Wang, H. & Zhang, G. (2014), 'The prevalence of hepatitis e virus infections among swine, swine farmers and the general population in Guangdong Province, China', *PLoS ONE* **9**(2).

Madden, R. G.; Wallace, S.; Sonderup, M.; Korsman, S.; Chivese, T.; Gavine, B.; Edem, A.; Govender, R.; English, N.; Kaiyamo, C.; Lutchman, O.; van der Eijk, A. A.; Pas, S. D.; Webb, G. W.; Palmer, J.; Goddard, E.; Wasserman, S.; Dalton, H. R. & Spearman, C. W. (2016), 'Hepatitis E virus: Western Cape, South Africa', *World Journal of Gastroenterology* **22**(44), 9853--9859.

Mansuy, J.; Sauné, K. B. Rech, H.; Abravanel, F.; Mengelle, C.; L'Homme, S.; Destruel, F.; Kamar, N. & Izopet, J. (2015), 'Seroprevalence in blood donors reveals widespread, multi-source exposure to hepatitis E virus, southern France, October 2011', *Eurosurveillance* **20**(19).

Mast, E. E.; Kuramoto, I. K.; Favorov, M. O.; Schoening, V. R.; Burkholder, B. T.; Shapiro, C. N. & Holland, P. V. (1997), 'Prevalence of and risk factors for antibody to hepatitis E virus seroreactivity among blood donors in Northern California.', *The Journal of infectious diseases* **176**(1), 34--40.

Meader, E.; Thomas, D.; Salmon, R. & Sillis, M. (2010), 'Seroprevalence of hepatitis E virus in the UK farming population.', *Zoonoses and Public Health* **57**(7-8), 504--509.

Mellgren, Å.; Karlsson, M.; Karlsson, M.; Lagging, M.; Wejstål, R. & Norder, H. (2017), 'High seroprevalence against hepatitis E virus in patients with chronic hepatitis C virus infection', *Journal of Clinical Virology* **88**, 39--45.

Meng, Q.-F.; You, H.-L.; Wang, W.-L.; Zhou, N.; Dong, W. & Cong, W. (2015), 'Seroprevalence and risk factors of hepatitis E virus infection among children in China', *Journal of Medical Virology* **87**(9), 1573--1577.

Meng, X.; Wiseman, B.; Elvinger, F.; Guenette, D.; Toth, T.; Engle, R.; Emerson, S. & Purcell, R. (2002), 'Prevalence of antibodies to hepatitis E virus in veterinarians working with swine and in normal blood donors in the United States and other countries', *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* **40**(1), 117--122.

Nübling, M.; Hofmann, F. & Tiller, F.-W. (2002), 'Occupational risk for hepatitis A and hepatitis E among health care professionals?', *Infection* **30**(2), 94--97.

Olsen, B. b.; Axelsson-Olsson, D.; Thelin, A. & Weiland, O. (2006), 'Unexpected high prevalence of IgG-antibodies to hepatitis E virus in Swedish pig farmers and controls', *Scandinavian Journal of Infectious Diseases* **38**(1), 55-58.

Pisano, M. B.; Balderramo, D.; Wassaf, M. M.; Lotto, M.; Carlino, Y.; Re, V. E. & Debes, J. D. (2016), 'Hepatitis E virus infection in patients on dialysis and in solid organ transplant recipients in Argentina: exploring associated risk factors.', *Archives of Virology*.

Psichogiou, M. A.; Tassopoulos, N. C.; Papatheodoridis, G. V.; Tzala, E.; Klarmann, R.;

Witteler, H.; Schlauder, G. G.; Troonen, H. & Hatzakis, A. (1995), 'Hepatitis E virus infection in a cohort of patients with acute non-A, non-B hepatitis.', *Journal of Hepatology* **23**(6), 668--673.

Rapicetta, M.; Monarca, R.; Kondili, L.; Chionne, P.; Madonna, E.; Madeddu, G.; Soddu, A.; Candido, A.; Carbonara, S.; Mura, M.; Starnini, G. & Babudieri, S. (2013), 'Hepatitis e virus and hepatitis A virus exposures in an apparently healthy high-risk population in Italy', *Infection* **41**(1), 69--76.

Riveiro-Barciela, M.; Buti, M. b.; Homs, M.; Campos-Varela, I.; Cantarell, C.; Crespo, M.; Castells, L.; Taberner, D.; Quer, J. b.; Esteban, R. b. & Rodriguez-Frías, F. c. (2014), 'Cirrhosis, liver transplantation and HIV infection are risk factors associated with hepatitis E virus infection', *PLoS ONE* **9**(7).

Saffar, M.; Farhadi, R.; Ajami, A.; Khalilian, A.; Babamahmudi, F. & Saffar, H. (2009), 'Seroepidemiology of hepatitis E virus infection in 2-25-year-olds in Sari district, Islamic Republic of Iran', *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal* **15**(1), 136--142.

Said, B.; Ijaz, S.; Chand, M. b.; Kafatos, G.; Tedder, R. c. d. & Morgan, D. (2014), 'Hepatitis e virus in England and Wales: Indigenous infection is associated with the consumption of processed pork products', *Epidemiology and Infection* **142**(7), 1467--1475.

Scotto, G.; Aucella, F.; Grandaliano, G.; Martinelli, D.; Querques, M.; Gesuete, A.; Infante, B.; Delli Carri, P.; Massa, S.; Salatino, G.; Bulla, F. & Fazio, V. (2015), 'Hepatitis E in hemodialysis and kidney transplant patients in South-East Italy', *World Journal of Gastroenterology* **21**(11), 3266--3273.

Shimakawa, Y.; Njai, H. F.; Takahashi, K.; Berg, L.; Ndow, G.; Jeng-Barry, A.; Ceesay, A.; Tamba, S.; Opoku, E.; Taal, M.; Akbar, S. M. F.; Arai, M.; D'Alessandro, U.; Taylor-Robinson, S. D.; Njie, R.; Mishiro, S.; Thursz, M. R. & Lemoine, M. (2016), 'Hepatitis E virus infection and acute-on-chronic liver failure in West Africa: a case-control study from The Gambia.', *Alimentary Pharmacology & Therapeutics* **43**(3), 375--384.

Taha, T.; Rusie, L.; Labrique, A.; Nyirenda, M.; Soko, D.; Kamanga, M.; Kumwenda, J.; Farazadegan, H.; Nelson, K. & Kumwenda, N. (2015), 'Seroprevalence for hepatitis e and other viral hepatitis among diverse populations, Malawi', *Emerging Infectious Diseases* **21**(7), 1174--1182.

Tei, S.; Kitajima, N.; Ohara, S.; Inoue, Y.; Miki, M.; Yamatani, T.; Yamabe, H.; Mishiro, S. & Kinoshita, Y. (2004), 'Consumption of uncooked deer meat as a risk factor for hepatitis E virus infection: An age- and sex-matched case-control study', *Journal of Medical Virology* **74**(1), 67--70.

Teixeira, J.; Mesquita, J. R.; Pereira, S. S.; Oliveira, R. M. S.; Abreu-Silva, J.; Rodrigues, A.; Myrmel, M.; Stene-Johansen, K.; Overbo, J.; Goncalves, G. & Nascimento, M. S. J. (2017), 'Prevalence of hepatitis E virus antibodies in workers occupationally exposed to swine in Portugal.', *Medical Microbiology and Immunology* **206**(1), 77--81.

Trautwein, C.; Kiral, G.; Tillmann, H.; Manns, M.; Witteler, H. & Michel, G. (1995), 'Risk

factors and prevalence of hepatitis E in German immigrants from the former soviet union', *Journal of Medical Virology* **45**(4), 429--434.

Tucker, T. d.; Kirsch, R.; Louw, S.; Isaacs, S.; Kannemeyer, J. & Robson, S. (1996), 'Hepatitis E in South Africa: Evidence for sporadic spread and increased seroprevalence in rural areas', *Journal of Medical Virology* **50**(2), 117--119.

Unzueta, A.; Valdez, R.; Chang, Y.-H.; Desmarteau, Y.; Heilman, R.; Scott, R.; Douglas, D. & Rakela, J. (2016), 'Hepatitis E virus serum antibodies and RNA prevalence in patients evaluated for heart and kidney transplantation', *Annals of Hepatology* **15**(1), 33--40.

Vaidya, S.; Tilekar, B.; Walimbe, A. & Arankalle, V. (2003), 'Increased Risk of Hepatitis E in Sewage Workers from India', *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine* **45**(11), 1167--1170.

Van Den Berg, B.; Van Der Eijk, A.; Pas, S.; Hunter, J. e.; Madden, R. e.; Tio-Gillen, A.; Dalton, H. e. & Jacobs, B. c. (2014), 'Guillain-Barré syndrome associated with preceding hepatitis E virus infection', *Neurology* **82**(6), 491--497.

Verhoef, L.; Koopmans, M.; Duizer, E.; Bakker, J.; Reimerink, J. & Van Pelt, W. (2012), 'Seroprevalence of hepatitis e antibodies and risk profile of HEV seropositivity in the Netherlands, 2006-2007', *Epidemiology and Infection* **140**(10), 1838--1847.

Vilibic-Cavlek, T.; Vilibic, M.; Kolaric, B.; Jemersic, L.; Kucinar, J.; Barbic, L.; Bagaric, A.; Stevanovic, V.; Tabain, I.; Sviben, M.; Jukic, V. & Mlinaric-Galinovic, G. (2016), 'Seroepidemiology of Hepatitis E in Selected Population Groups in Croatia: A Prospective Pilot Study', *Zoonoses and Public Health* **63**(6), 494--502.

Villalba, M.; Guan, M.; Pérez, A.; Corredor, M.; Frometa, S.; Moreno, A.; Hu, W.; Howard, T.; Lay, L. & Anderson, D. (2010), 'Seroprevalence of antibodies to hepatitis E virus in two large communities in Havana, Cuba', *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* **104**(12), 772--776.

Villalba, M. d. l. C. M.; Owot, J. C.; Correia, B.; Corredor, M. B.; Flaquet, P. P.; Frometa, S. S.; Wong, M. S. & Lay, L. d. l. Án. R. (2013), 'Hepatitis E virus genotype 3 in humans and swine, Cuba', *Infection, Genetics and Evolution* **14**, 335 -- 339.

Vitral, C. b.; da Silva-Nunes, M.; Pinto, M.; de Oliveira, J.; Gaspar, A.; Pereira, R. & Ferreira, M. (2014), 'Hepatitis A and E seroprevalence and associated risk factors: A community-based cross-sectional survey in rural Amazonia', *BMC Infectious Diseases* **14**(1).

Wichmann, O.; Schimanski, S.; Koch, J.; Kohler, M.; Rothe, C.; Plentz, A.; Jilg, W. & Stark, K. (2008), 'Phylogenetic and case-control study on hepatitis E virus infection in Germany.', *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* **198**(12), 1732--1741.

Wong, K. d.; Liu, Y.; Ng, P.; Young, B. & Lee, S. (2004), 'Epidemiology of Hepatitis A and Hepatitis E Infection and Their Determinants in Adult Chinese Community in Hong Kong', *Journal of Medical Virology* **72**(4), 538--544.

Wu, J.-C. c.; Sheen, I.-J.; Chiang, T.-Y.; Sheng, W.-Y.; Wang, Y.-J.; Chan, C.-Y. & Lee, S.-D. (1998), 'The impact of traveling to endemic areas on the spread of hepatitis E virus infection: Epidemiological and molecular analyses', *Hepatology* **27**(5), 1415--1420.

Yoon, Y.; Jeong, H. S.; Yun, H.; Lee, H.; Hwang, Y.-S.; Park, B.; Lee, C. J.; Lee, S. & Hyeon, J.-Y. (2014), 'Hepatitis E Virus (HEV) Seroprevalence in the general population of the Republic of Korea in 2007-2009: a nationwide cross-sectional study', *BMC Infectious Diseases* **14**.

Zheng, Y.; Ge, S.; Zhang, J.; Guo, Q.; Ng, M.; Wang, F.; Xia, N. & Jiang, Q. (2006), 'Swine as a principal reservoir of hepatitis E virus that infects humans in Eastern China', *Journal of Infectious Diseases* **193**(12), 1643--1649.

6 Supplementary tables and figures of the effects of handling on the transmission of hepatitis E infection

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of hepatitis E infection by consumption of beef (n=3), pork (n=21), other red meats (n=21) and non-specific meats (n=22) in the combined mixed (n=53), immunocompromised (n=7) and pregnant (n=7) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All	Base	0.464	0.107	51	[0.254 – 0.673]	<.0001
(19 stud)	Raw or undercooked	0.376	0.214	16	[-0.044 – 0.796]	0.079
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1133	QE(df=65)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.3032	p<.0001			
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.067
	Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of hepatitis E by consumption of red meats

Table S2. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of hepatitis E infection by consumption of fresh vegetables in the combined mixed (n=12), immunocompromised (n=1) and pregnant (n=4) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All (11 stud)	Base	0.088	0.024	4	[0.042 – 0.135]	<.0001
	Raw	-0.028	0.102	6	[-0.228 – 0.171]	0.781
	Unwashed	0.325	0.200	7	[-0.066 – 0.718]	0.100
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=14)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.2692	p=0.9312			
	Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0002			0.190
	Points removed	0				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of hepatitis E by consumption of vegetables